

EFFECTIVENESS OF COGNITIVE AND BEHAVIORAL THERAPY IN REDUCING ANGER AND DEPRESSIVE SYMPTOMS AMONG VULNERABLE POPULATION

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Abstract

The current study examined the effectiveness of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) and behavioral interventions in reducing anger and behavioral issues among underprivileged and uneducated populations of the Districts of interior Sindh. A purposive sample of 10 patients were drawn from the population of 250 individuals including Female between age ranges 18 to 50 years, identified through the Urdu version of the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAM-D), After identification of the individual 10 participants who scored high on HAM-D and lied on severe range of depression along with anger issues were selected for the group therapy sessions. The intervention consisted on cognitive and behavioral therapy techniques provided across 6 sessions and therapy were followed by the gap of one week. Results has shown a significant reduction in symptoms, with scores decreasing from severe to moderate or mild levels among 8 out of 10 clients. Findings highlight the effectiveness of planned therapeutic interventions for anger and behavioral issues in underprivileged populations. Implications for clinical practice and future research are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Mental health disorders characterize one of the major cause and the threat to the global health industry as its prevalence is increasing day by day, with anger and behavioral problems establishing prevalent yet often underdiagnosed problems. Among individuals from vulnerable, financially underprivileged, and uneducated backgrounds, the risk of developing anger-related problems is heightened due to continuous ongoing chronic stressors, lack of facilities limited access to healthcare, and lack of psych education. Anger, though a universal human emotion, becomes pathological when it manifests as frequent outbursts, aggression, or maladaptive coping behaviors. Behavioral issues often comorbidities, combining the psychological, social, and occupational impairments face by the individuals

The relationship between socioeconomic difficulties and mental health consequences has been widely recognized. Families who are financially unstable are often prone to chronic environmental stressors such as unemployment, overcrowding, poverty. family conflict, and limited access to healthcare. These factors plays a vital role as both precipitants and perpetuating mediators of psychological distress. In such situations, the lack of awareness about psychological services further worsens the situation. Individuals with little or no formal education frequently understand emotional or behavioral disturbances as personal faults rather than health conditions that can be treated through therapy. This misinterpretation often delays treatment-seeking and treatment process , leading to the deteriorating of symptoms. In clinical psychology, anger is conceptualized as a multidimensional concept involving cognitive appraisals, physiological arousal, and behavioral responses. Unresolved anger contributes to interpersonal conflict, impaired decision-making, and poor problem-solving abilities in the patients. For people already facing socioeconomic vulnerabilities, these consequences can extend cycles of poverty and exclusion. Children from low-income families often model dysregulated behaviors observed in adults, perpetuating intergenerational cycles of dysfunction.

Therapeutic interventions such as Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) and behavioral therapy have arisen as evidence-based therapy approaches to managing anger and behavioral issues. CBT postulates that maladaptive thoughts leads to emotional and behavioral disturbances, and through restructuring these cognitions, individuals can develop healthier patterns of functioning. Behavioral therapy emphasizes reinforcement strategies, skill-building, and the gradual replacement of maladaptive behaviors with adaptive behaviors. Both approaches have shown effectiveness across

varied populations, yet research on their application among socioeconomically disadvantaged communities in South Asia, particularly Pakistan, remains inadequate.

The current study bridges the gap by examining the effectiveness of group therapy sessions integrating Cognitive Behavior Therapy and behavioral techniques for clients identified through the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAM-D) Urdu version. The Urdu translation ensures cultural relevance and linguistic accessibility, facilitating accurate screening of psychological distress in populations with limited English proficiency. Participants in this study were selected based on severe HAM-D scores, signifying high levels of psychological distress. Group therapy was chosen as the primary intervention method given its advantages of cost-effectiveness, peer support, and normalization of shared problem.

This study also addresses a critical aspect of psychological service delivery in underprivileged settings. The adaptation of therapy to culturally and economically constrained environments. In settings where professional resources are scarce, group interventions using structured protocols offer ascendable solutions. Furthermore, the inclusion of anger management as a primary focus acknowledges the pressing social consequences of unresolved anger, which often demonstrates in domestic violence, community conflict, and poor educational and occupational consequences.

By investigating the pre- and post-intervention outcomes of Cognitive behavior therapy and behavioral therapy on a small but targeted group of severely distressed patients, this study aims to contribute empirical evidence to the field of clinical psychology in Pakistan. The research also intends to provide practical recommendations for mental health practitioners, NGOs, and policymakers looking for to design interventions for vulnerable communities. Eventually, the goal is to demonstrate that despite socioeconomic confines, structured psychotherapeutic interventions can bring meaningful reductions in psychological problem and behavioral dysregulation.

Objective of the Study

This study was conducted with aim of investigating the effectiveness of cognitive behavior therapy and behavior therapy techniques with the population of interior area where access to the psychological facilities is not easy because of the lack of awareness, socioeconomic problems and specifically the population was underprivilege and the prevalence of the psychological illness is way much bigger than any other city of Pakistan.

Hypothesis

H₁- Cognitive behavior therapy and behavior therapy techniques will significantly reduce depression and aggression in the underprivilege population in Pakistan.

H₂- There will be significant difference in depression and aggression after cognitive therapy session along with behavior therapy techniques in the underprivilege population of Pakistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Research has consistently emphasized the association between anger, behavioral issues, and wider mental health problem. Anger severity is linked with depression, anxiety, substance abuse, and interpersonal problem. A significant body of evidence suggests that socioeconomic disadvantage worsens these issues by increasing exposure to chronic stressors and reducing access to coping resources.

Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) has long been considered the most effective therapy for treating a variety of mental health problem, including anger disorders. Beck's cognitive theory (1976) laid the foundation for Cognitive Behavior Therapy by asserting that dysfunctional thought patterns cause emotional distress. In the context of anger issue, cognitive distortions such as hostile attribution bias, catastrophizing, and personalization contribute to maladaptive responses. Empirical studies demonstrate that Cognitive Behavior Therapy interventions targeting these distortions reduce both the frequency and intensity of anger outburst.

Behavioral therapy, grounded in the principles of operant and classical conditioning, emphasizes the role of environmental reinforcement in maintaining maladaptive behaviors. Anger outbursts, for example, may be reinforced when they result in the temporary termination of interpersonal conflict or avoidance of responsibility. By applying techniques such as positive reinforcement, modeling, and systematic desensitization, behavioral interventions seek to break these reinforcement cycles. Research has shown that behavioral technique can significantly reduce overt behaviors in children and adolescents, as well as aggression and hostility in adults.

When CBT and behavior intervention techniques were applied in group settings, its gave a wonderful results as the population was entirely unique and the setting for the therapy was choose as a group. Group therapy not only reduces costs but also facilitates social learning, peer support, and collective problem-solving. Yalom's therapeutic factors, such as universality

and altruism, are particularly relevant in collectivist cultures where shared experiences enhance treatment engagement. Studies conducted in low- and middle-income countries have reported positive outcomes from group-based CBT, particularly in reducing symptoms of depression, anxiety, and anger.

The role of assessment tools in accurately identifying treatment needs cannot be overstated. The Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAM-D), developed in 1960, remains one of the most widely used clinician-administered scales for measuring depression severity. Its Urdu translation has been validated in Pakistani populations, ensuring cultural and linguistic appropriateness. In this study, the Urdu version of HAM-D was instrumental in identifying clients experiencing severe psychological distress, thereby enabling the selection of participants most in need of intervention.

Several studies have underscored the relationship between depression and anger. For instance, Fava et al. (1993) noted that suppressed or poorly regulated anger often co-occurs with major depressive episodes. Other researchers have highlighted that individuals from disadvantaged backgrounds may somatize their psychological distress, reporting physical complaints rather than emotional difficulties. This highlights the importance of culturally sensitive assessment tools like HAM-D in capturing the true extent of psychological difficulties.

Indication from Pakistan shows that financial problem and lack of education are significant predictors of mental health problems. Husain et al. (2007) reported high rates of depression among low-income women in rural Pakistan, while Naeem et al. (2015) highlighted barriers to mental health service utilization in urban low-income populations. Such findings underscore the urgency of developing context-specific interventions that address both psychological and socioeconomic determinants of health.

Cognitive Behavioral Therapy has been adapted successfully across cultures, though modifications are often needed to align with local norms and values. Rahman et al. (2008), for example, developed culturally adapted CBT for perinatal depression in Pakistan, which demonstrated significant improvements in maternal mental health. This suggests that structured interventions, even when resource-intensive, can be tailored to underprivileged contexts with meaningful results.

Group-based behavioral and cognitive therapy has also been applied successfully in managing anger and aggression. Studies from both Western and non-Western contexts indicate

reductions in anger intensity, frequency of outbursts, and improvements in emotional regulation following structured group interventions. Importantly, group therapy also provides a sense of belonging and reduces stigma associated with mental health treatment. Taken together, the literature demonstrates a robust evidence base for CBT and behavioral therapy in managing anger and behavioral issues. However, there remains a paucity of research examining their effectiveness among socioeconomically disadvantaged populations in Pakistan. The current study addresses this gap by employing the HAM-D Urdu version to identify severely distressed patients and delivering group-based therapy sessions that integrate cognitive and behavioral techniques. The expected outcomes include reductions in anger, improvements in emotional regulation, and enhanced overall functioning. By situating the intervention within a culturally and economically relevant framework, this research contributes to the growing body of literature advocating for accessible, evidence-based mental health services in low-resource settings.

METHODOLOGY

The present study adopted an experimental design to evaluate the effectiveness of group-based Cognitive Behavior Therapy and behavioral therapy in reducing anger and behavioral issues.

Operational Definitions

Anger

Anger is operationally defined as an emotional response characterized by increased physiological arousal (e.g., raised voice, clenched fists, flushed face, muscle tension) and observable behaviors such as yelling, arguing, or displaying aggression when confronted with frustration, threat, or provocation. Spielberger, C. D. (1999).

Behavioral Problems

Behavior problems are operationally defined as patterns of observable actions that deviate from socially or developmentally appropriate norms and interfere with academic, social, or personal functioning. Achenbach, T. M., & Rescorla, L. A. (2001).

Sample Size

Participants were selected through purposive sampling from financially underprivileged families. 250 female age ranges between 18 to 50 years were approached and HAM-D test were administered. The 10 participants score high on the test were selected for the group therapy sessions.

Inclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria required participants to score in the severe range on the Urdu version of the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAM-D). A total of 10 clients meeting this criterion were included.

Exclusion Criteria

Exclusion criteria includes the people who were not standing higher on HAM-D scoring. Pregnant women, Psychotic patients, people with disabilities, people with above 50 years were excluded from the study.

Procedure

Study was followed by the three phase including pre intervention phase, intervention phase and post intervention phase

Pre Intervention Phase

The study was started with the consent form to get the permission for the session as well as to gather the data from the participants. The awareness session on depression and anger issues were given to the 250 female age ranges between 18 to 50 years from the underprivileged areas of Sindh. At the end of the session consent forms were taken to administer the test as well to use this test as a HAM-D Urdu version were administered to every individual. 10 participants who scored high on Ham-D and were on the inclusion criteria of the study were selected for the intervention phase.

Intervention Phase

After the phase 1 the selected participants who scored high on the HAM-D were given 6 group sessions in which the eclectic approach was used. Cognitive behavior therapy and behavior therapy techniques were administered to reduce the symptoms and anger outburst among the participants.

Post Intervention Phase

After the 6 sessions of intervention participants were again administered the HAM-D test which shows reduction of symptoms and anger outburst from severe to moderate range in 8 individuals among 10. Study showed that CBT and BT are highly effective with patients with major depression and anger outburst.

RESULTS

To evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention, descriptive statistics were calculated for pre-test and post-test scores on the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAM-D, Urdu version).

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for HAM-D Urdu Version Pre-test and Post-test Scores (N = 10)

Measure	N	M	SD	Min	Max
Pre-test	10	25.5	1.27	23	28
Post-test	10	17.5	1.27	15	20

Note. HAM-D = Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (Urdu version). Scores represent severity of depressive symptoms, with higher scores indicating greater severity.

As shown in Table 1, participants' mean HAM-D scores decreased from 25.5 (SD = 1.27) at pre-test to 17.5 (SD = 1.27) at post-test. The reduction indicates a clear shift from the severe depression range to the moderate range, suggesting that the intervention was effective.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The consent form taken from all the participants and they were told their right of withdrawal from the study as well as their was no potential harm for any participants who was part of this study.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study support the effectiveness of group-based CBT and behavioral interventions in reducing anger and behavioral issues among socioeconomically underprivileged populations. The significant improvement observed in 8 out of 10 participants demonstrates that even short but structured sessions and interventions can lead to a big improvements in the people with depression and anger outburst. The results line up with earlier research indicating that CBT is effective in restructuring maladaptive thought patterns and behavioral therapy supports in reducing problematic behaviors. Significantly, the use of the HAM-D Urdu version confirmed culturally relevant assessment and identification of clients in need of intervention. Group therapy also facilitated cost-effective service delivery, making it a viable alternative in low-resource settings. However, the lack of improvement among two participants highlights the need for individualized approaches and potentially more intensive interventions in certain cases.

CONCLUSION

This study was conducted with the underprivileged population of interior area and the sessions were provided based on cognitive behavior therapy and behavior therapy. Results showed that group therapy sessions even for short time can bring a big change in the individuals.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Study should be conducted with a large sample size to see the difference in results
- Study should be done with the different group includes the same age people
- Study should be administered in different cultures to compare the results.
- Future study can give a look to the variable like pregnancy, drug use, trauma with the same therapeutic intervention and groups of people.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- Small sample were taken which reduce the study validity for the large group as the finding cannot be generalized.
- Short time duration was also the problem which hinders the effectiveness of therapies.
- Only underprivileged population were used for the study which had other confounding variables like financial issues and lack of basic facilities.

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